

Physicochemistry shapes bioactivity landscape of pan-ABC transporter modulators: Anchor point for innovative Alzheimer's disease therapeutics

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a devastating neurological disorder characterized by the pathological accumulation of macromolecular A β and tau leading to neuronal death. Drugs approved to treat AD may ameliorate disease symptoms, however, no curative treatment exists. A β peptides were discovered to be substrates of adenosine triphosphate-(ATP)-binding cassette (ABC) transporters. Activators of these membrane-bound efflux proteins that promote binding and/or translocation of A β could revolutionize AD medicine. The knowledge about ABC transporter activators is very scarce, however, the few molecules that were reported contain substructural features of multitarget (pan-)ABC transporter inhibitors. A cutting-edge strategy to obtain new drug candidates is to explore and potentially exploit the recently proposed multitarget binding site of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors as anchor point for the development of innovative activators to promote A β clearance from the brain. Molecular associations between functional bioactivities and physicochemical properties of small-molecules are key to understand these processes. This study provides an analysis of a recently reported unique multitarget dataset for the correlation between multitarget bioactivity and physicochemistry. Six novel pan-ABC transporter inhibitors were validated containing substructural features of ABC transporter activators, which underpins the relevance of the multitarget binding site for the targeted development of novel AD diagnostics and therapeutics.

1. Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disease which is accompanied by behavioral changes and cognitive impairments, and thus, AD hampers the ability to take part in every-day-life activities [1,2]. Besides intraneuronal neurofibrillary tangles (NFT) of the microtubule-associated hyperphosphorylated protein tau [2], extracellular A β aggregates ('plaques') consisting of mostly oligomeric A β polypeptides of lengths between 37 and 43 amino acids are indicative of

post mortem AD diagnosis [3]. A β is generated through cleavage of the membrane-bound amyloid- β precursor protein (APP) mediated by β - and γ -secretase complexes [2]. A β plaques disrupt neurite function, interfere with synaptic communication, and impair cortico-cortical circuits [1,2]. Thus, A β is believed to be the initiator and major contributor to AD development and progression. According to the World Alzheimer Report 2021 [4], there are over 55 million people suffering from AD and related dementias. The number is expected to rise over 78 million worldwide in 2030, and it is estimated that not even a quarter of patients is diagnosed. This prospect represents a huge socio-economic burden for

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Nomenclature	
A β	amyloid-beta
ABC transporter	ATP-binding cassette transporter
ABC_BPMDs	well-studied ABC transporter-focusing binary pattern multitarget dataset
AD	Alzheimer's disease
ADME	absorption, distribution, metabolism, execution
APP	amyloid- β precursor protein
AR	adrenergic receptor
ATP	adenosine triphosphate
BBB	blood-brain barrier
BCRP	breast cancer resistance protein (ABCG2)
CLogP	calculated octanol/water coefficient
CNS	central nervous system
cryo-EM	cryogenic electron microscopy
GPCR	G-protein coupled receptor
IC	ion channel
IC ₅₀	half-maximal inhibition concentration
MSD	membrane-spanning domain
MR	molar refractivity
MW	molecular weight
MRP1	multidrug resistance-associated protein 1 (ABCC1)
NBD	nucleotide binding domain
NFT	neurofibrillary tangles
P-gp	P-glycoprotein (ABCB1)
SEM	standard error of the mean
SLC	solute carrier transporter
TPSA	topological polar surface area

communities, caregivers, and the patients themselves. Unfortunately, no effective and curative treatment against AD exists.

Several independent studies have demonstrated that A β macromolecules interact with adenosine-triphosphate-(ATP)-binding cassette (ABC) transport proteins [1,3,5–7]. Particularly, the well-studied ABC transporters ABCB1 (P-glycoprotein, P-gp), ABCC1 (multidrug resistance-associated protein 1, MRP1), and ABCG2 (breast cancer resistance protein, BCRP) are associated with direct clearance of A β from the AD brain to the blood stream over the blood-brain barrier (BBB) [1,5]:

- (i) In terms of ABCB1, a direct interaction with A β was proven, which was sensitive to selective ABCB1 inhibition [8]. Furthermore, ABCB1 inhibition or knock-out led to (a) an overload of cerebral A β due to endogenous A β (over)production [9,10] and (b) an increase of A β flow from the apical to the basolateral side of the BBB, concluding ABCB1 to be a ‘gatekeeper’ that prevents blood-borne A β from entering the brain [11–13]. In addition, aggregation and deposition of A β and expression of ABCB1 correlated inversely [14,15], leading to the conclusion that A β downregulates ABCB1 expression [14–16]. Finally, induction of ABCB1 restored cerebral clearance of A β [17].
- (ii) With respect to ABCC1, knock-out of this transporter was reflected in an extreme cerebral increase in A β burden [5], while induction and/or functional activation of ABCC1 reduced the levels of cerebral A β by 50 % [5,18], leading to the conclusion that ABCC1 may also directly interact with A β polypeptides.
- (iii) Regarding ABCG2, a direct interaction with A β was proven [19]. Furthermore, ABCG2 inhibition or knock-out led to a larger cerebral A β burden due to an increased flow of A β from the apical to the basolateral side of the BBB, deducing ABCG2's role as ‘gatekeeper’ [13,19,20].

The discovery of small-molecule activators that establish an interaction and/or binding affinity between A β and ABC transport proteins leading to increased transport capacity for A β is desirable. However, although ABC transporter activators have generally been described in the literature, the knowledge about such agents is very limited, hindering the development of computational models to predict and discover new lead molecules. Luckily, the knowledge about inhibitors of ABC transporters is much more pronounced [21–23]. Particularly, multitarget (pan-)ABC transporter inhibitors may provide a promising prospect in terms of the development of innovative anti-AD agents: A common ‘multitarget binding site’ amongst ABC transporters in general has been proposed [22–26], and many pan-ABC transporter inhibitors share substructural features of ABC transporter activators [27]. These substructural features include basic scaffolds and other substructural

elements that promote multitargeting of ABC transporters, as for example, chromone [e.g., ABCC1 activator 1 (compound 4e) [27,28] and focused [24] pan-ABC transporter inhibitor 2 (compound 48) [21,29]], indole [e.g., ABCC1 activator 3 (indomethacin) [27,30] and focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitor 4 (compound 7) [21,31]], 1,2,4-oxadiazole [e.g., ABCB1 activator 5 (QB12) [32] and focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitor 6 (compound 26) [21,23]], pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidine [e.g., ABCC1 activator 7 (compound 6) [27,33]], differential modulator 8 (compound 9) [27,33], focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitor 9 (compound 55) [21,34], and standard ABCC1 inhibitor 10 (compound 56) [21,34]], quinazoline [e.g., ABCB1 activator 11 (prazosin) [27,35] and focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitor 12 (compound 21) [21,23]], tetrahydroisoquinoline [e.g., ABCB1 activator 13 (compound 13) [36] and focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitor 14 (MC18) [21,37]], or thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine [e.g., ABCB1 activator 15 (QB13) [32] and focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitor 16 (compound 14) [21,38]]. Fig. 1 provides the molecular formulas of the mentioned compounds. The bridge between ABC transporter activation and inhibition has also been stressed in certain reports about molecules from the very same structural class, also in the context of AD [33,36]. These findings reveal the high relevance of shared substructural features in terms of drug discovery, design, and development of potential anti-AD drugs.

Multitarget fingerprints to extract potentially bioactive pan-ABC transporter inhibitors from large compound libraries have very recently been described [22,23,25]. However, these substructural pattern-based fingerprints may not be sufficient to downsize ultra-large compound libraries, e.g., the Enamine *REAL SPACE* library consisting of over 22.7 billion compounds (effective July 2022; steadily growing). More descriptors are needed to complement the multitarget fingerprints to support the discovery of novel and innovative drugs. Physicochemical properties, such as the calculated octanol/water coefficient (CLogP) [39–42], molecular weight (MW) [41–44], molar refractivity (MR) [41], and the topological polar surface area (TPSA) [43,45] have frequently been analyzed in terms of the bioactivity of compounds against ABC transporters [39–45], but also other pharmacological targets, such as adrenergic receptors (ARs) [46], G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs) [47], ion channels (ICs) [48] or solute carrier transporters (SLCs) [49]. Specifically, the role of ABC transporters in the ADME model (pharmacokinetic aspects of drug absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion) and their contribution to central nervous system (CNS) penetration have been disclosed [44,50,51]. If not working on brain vessel endothelia, CNS penetration is significantly important for anti-AD drugs to be effective and depends strongly on ABC transporter activity at the BBB [52]. Physicochemical properties have frequently been used in the selection processes of computational approaches to discriminate between potentially active and inactive molecules with respect to ABC transporters [22,23,25,38], and were also placed into the context of AD

Fig. 1. Depiction of substructural features (red) that are shared amongst activators of ABC transporters and focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

[53]. However, their true impact on polypharmacology has never been investigated, and their contribution to the differentiation between selective and multitarget modulation is unexplored.

Recently, we reported on a curated binary pattern multitarget dataset (ABC_BPMDS) of small-molecules that were all evaluated against the well-studied ABC transporters ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 [21]. The ABC_BPMDS interconnects bioactivities against several pharmacological targets, and thus, presents a multi-dimensional pharmacological landscape of ABC transporter inhibitors (www.panabc.info) [21,54,55]. In the present report, we provide for the first time insights into the distinct features of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors compared to selective ABCB1,

ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors with respect to physicochemical properties [21]. Six novel pan-ABC transporter inhibitors were analyzed for their physicochemical properties and compared to the peculiarities of the postulated 'multitarget binding site'. By exploring the proposed multitarget binding site, novel, innovative, and curative AD diagnostics and therapeutics may be developed.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data acquisition and processing

2.1.1. Compilation of the ABC_BPMDS

The ABC_BPMDS consisting of 1167 compounds was manually assembled from 113 reports between 1994 and 2022 after a deep literature search at the National Center for Biotechnological Information (NCBI) [21–23]. The curation of the data was conducted as reported earlier [21] using ChemDraw Pro version 20.1.1.125 (PerkinElmer Informatics, Waltham, MA, USA) and GraphPad Prism version 8.4.0 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). Compounds were qualified to be listed if they were assessed toward all three targets, and only functional assays of active transport processes (e.g., fluorescence or radioactivity measurement) were accepted, excluding assays for which the surrogate parameter (measured value) is not directly connected to the active transport [e.g., ATPase assays (phosphate release) or MDR reversal assays (cell viability)] [21,23]. The physicochemical properties ClogP, MW, MR, and TPSA were calculated using Molecular Operating Environment (MOE) version 2019.01 (Chemical Computing Group, Montreal, QC, Canada) [21].

2.1.2. Classification of compounds

The 1167 compounds were classified according to their (poly)pharmacological profile: (i) Class 0: inactive compounds; (ii) Class 1: selective ABCB1 inhibitors; (iii) Class 2: selective ABCC1 inhibitors; (iv) Class 3: selective ABCG2 inhibitors; (v) Class 4: dual ABCB1 and ABCC1 inhibitors; (vi) Class 5: dual ABCB1 and ABCG2 inhibitors; (vii) Class 6: dual ABCC1 and ABCG2 inhibitors; and (viii) Class 7: triple ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors [23,25]. The portion of Classes 1, 2, 3, and 7 amongst the ABC_BPMDS can be found in Fig. 2 A. These Classes

were further sub-classified according to their bioactivities: (i) Outstanding Class 1/2/3 (IC_{50} values $<0.1 \mu\text{M}$); (ii) Extraordinary Class 1/2/3 (IC_{50} values $<1 \mu\text{M}$); (iii) Superior Class 1/2/3 (IC_{50} values $<5 \mu\text{M}$); (iv) Medium Class 1/2/3 (IC_{50} values $<10 \mu\text{M}$); (v) Semi Class 1/2/3: IC_{50} values $\leq 15 \mu\text{M}$; (vi) Weak Class 1/2/3 (IC_{50} values $\geq 15 \mu\text{M}$); (vii) Very Weak Class 1/2/3: IC_{50} values $\geq 20 \mu\text{M}$). This sub-classification accounted for 88, 61, and 409 selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors, respectively. Class 7 compounds were sub-classified as reported earlier [22]: (i) Superior Class 7 (IC_{50} values $<5 \mu\text{M}$); (ii) Medium Class 7 (IC_{50} values $<10 \mu\text{M}$ and at least one IC_{50} value between 5 and $<10 \mu\text{M}$); (iii) Semi Class 7: IC_{50} values $\leq 15 \mu\text{M}$ and at least one IC_{50} value between 10 and $\leq 15 \mu\text{M}$); (iv) Weak Class 7: two IC_{50} values $\geq 20 \mu\text{M}$ and one IC_{50} value $<10 \mu\text{M}$; and (v) Very Weak Class 7: two IC_{50} values $\geq 20 \mu\text{M}$ and one IC_{50} value $\geq 10 \mu\text{M}$). This sub-classification included 117 focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors, while 70 could not be sub-classified. Fig. 2 shows the sub-classifications for Class 1 (B), Class 2 (C), Class 3 (D), and Class 7 (E) compounds.

2.1.3. Bioactivity–physicochemistry linear regression analysis

The bioactivity data of the 1167 compounds of the ABC_BPMDS expressed as half-maximal inhibition concentration (IC_{50}) were translated into pIC_{50} values by using the negative decadic logarithm of the IC_{50} values. Mean and standard error of the mean (SEM) values were generated for each physicochemical property of each Sub-Class. The respective bioactivity–physicochemistry value pairs were plotted and a bidirectional one-phase linear regression was conducted using GraphPad Prism version 8.4.0. For the multidirectional two-phase linear regression analysis, the highest Sub-Class category of each Class was used as reference value and the compounds of the other Sub-Classes were divided into two sub-populations, allocating compounds with numeric physicochemistry values below ('left') and above ('right') of

Fig. 2. (Sub-)classification of compounds of the ABC_BPMDS (A–E) and simplified legend of sub-classification (F).

reference value. Mean and SEM values of the sub-populations were calculated, and a bidirectional one-phase linear regression analysis was conducted for each sub-population using the reference value as fix point for the upper end of the regression lines.

2.2. Biological assessment

2.2.1. Chemicals

The standard ABCB1 (cyclosporine A) and ABCG2 (Ko143) inhibitors were delivered by Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA), and the standard ABCC1 inhibitor **10** was synthesized as reported previously [34]. The fluorescence dyes calcein AM, daunorubicin, Hoechst 33342, and pheophorbide A were purchased from Calbiochem (EMD Chemicals, San Diego, USA), EMD Millipore (Billerica, MA, USA), and Cayman Chemicals (Ann Arbor, MI, USA). All other chemicals were obtained from Alfa Aesar (Haverhill, MA, USA) and VWR (Radnor, PA, USA). Compounds **17–22** were stored as 10 mM stocks at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Dilution series and the experimental cell culture were performed either with phenol red-free RPMI-1640 (GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA) or with phenol red-free Dulbecco's modified eagle media (DMEM; GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA) without further supplements.

2.2.2. Validation compounds

Six novel focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors have been identified in our compound library that were evaluated in terms of their bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape. The compounds were obtained either commercially (Enamine; **17–18** and **20–21**) or via organic synthesis (**19** and **22**): compound **17** [Name: 3-(thieno-[2,3-*b*]pyridin-5-yl)-5-(4-(thiomorpholinomethyl)phenyl)-1,2,4-oxadiazole; Catalog ID: Z2617318178; Link: <https://enaminestore.com/catalog/Z2617318178>; SMILES: N1(CC(C=C2) = CC=C2C3 = NC(C4 = CC(C=C5) = C5N=C4) = NO3)CCSCC1; purity: 90 %]; compound **18** [Name: 5-(1-(6-chloropyridazin-3-yl)piperidin-4-yl)-3-(thieno[2,3-*b*]pyridin-5-yl)-1,2,4-oxadiazole; Catalog ID: Z2617316123; Link: <https://enaminestore.com/catalog/Z2617316123>; SMILES: ClC(N=N1) = CC=C1N(CC2)CCC2C3 = NC(C4 = CC(C=C5) = C5N=C4) = NO3; purity: 90 %]; compound **19** [Name: 10-propyl-10*H*-phenothiazine; synthesis: phenothiazine (313 mg; 1.57 mmol) and 1-bromopropane (286 μL ; 3.14 mmol) were dissolved in anhydrous dimethylformamide (DMF; 2 mL) in the microwave-sealed tube under Argon. The mixture was subjected to microwave irradiation (200 W) at $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and purified via column chromatography using mobile phase petroleum ether/ethyl acetate (PE/EA = 20:1) affording product compound **19** as a brownish solid; yield: 15 %; purity (LC-MS): $>98\%$ %; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3 -*d*): δ 7.17–7.11 (m, 4H), 6.94–6.88 (m, 2H), 6.88–6.83 (m, 2H), 3.82 (t, 2H), 1.90–1.77 (m, 2H), 1.01 (t, $J = 7.4\text{ Hz}$, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 145.46, 127.55, 127.29, 125.06, 122.44, 115.54, 49.26, 20.29, 11.49; HRMS (ESI⁺): found as both protonated $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ [calculated for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{NS}^+$ (m/z), 242.09980; found, 242.09978] and neutral $[\text{M}]$ [calculated for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NS}$ (m/z), 241.09252; found, 241.09242] species; compound **20** [Name: 2-((9*H*-purin-6-yl)thio)-1-(2-(methylthio)-10*H*-phenothiazin-10-yl)ethan-1-one; catalog ID: Z1227796155; Link: <https://enaminestore.com/catalog/Z1227796155>; SMILES: O=C(N1C(C=CC=C2) = C2SC3 = C1C=C(SC)C=C3)CSC4 = NC=NC5 = C4N=CNS; purity: 90 %]; compound **21** [Name: 1-(7-bromo-2-chloro-5*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-yl)-6-methoxyoctahydro-3,5-methanocyclopenta[*b*]pyrrole; catalog ID: Z2613155266 Link: <https://enaminestore.com/catalog/Z2613155266>; SMILES: COC1C(C2)CC3C2C1N (C4 = NC(Cl) = NC5 = C4NC=C5Br)C3; purity: 90 %]; compound **22** [Name: *N,N'*-(1,3-phenylenebis(methylene))bis(thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine); synthesis: 4-chloro-thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (600 mg; 3.52 mmol) was suspended in absolute ethanol (EtOH; 5 mL) in the microwave-sealed tube, and *m*-xylylenediamine (233 μL ; 1.76 mmol) as well as *N,N*-diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA; 613 μL ; 3.52 mmol) were subsequently added. The mixture was subjected to microwave irradiation (100 W) at $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for

30 min. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and purified via column chromatography using mobile phase dichloromethane/methanol/ammonium hydroxide 25 % in H_2O (DCM/MeOH/ $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} = 9:1:0.1$) affording product compound **22** that was further precipitated from MeOH as a white solid; yield: 56 %; purity (LC-MS): $>99\%$ %; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 8.51 (t, $J = 6.0\text{ Hz}$, 2H), 8.28 (s, 2H), 7.62 (d, $J = 6.0\text{ Hz}$, 2H), 7.56 (d, $J = 6.0\text{ Hz}$, 2H), 7.39–7.35 (m, 1H), 7.30–7.20 (m, 3H), 4.72 (d, $J = 6.0\text{ Hz}$, 4H); ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO): δ 165.58, 156.81, 153.68, 139.67, 128.35, 126.12, 125.80, 122.74, 119.28, 116.09, 43.15; HRMS (ESI⁺): $[\text{M} + 2\text{H}]^{2+}$ [calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2^+$ (m/z), 203.05117; found, 203.05133].

2.2.3. Cell culture

The ABCB1-overexpressing A2780/ADR, ABCC1-overexpressing H69AR, and ABCG2-overexpressing MDCK II BCRP cell lines were a generous gift of Prof. Dr. Finn K. Hansen and Prof. Dr. Gerd Bendas (Pharmaceutical and Cellbiological Chemistry, University of Bonn, Germany). A2780/ADR and H69AR cells were cultured in RPMI-1640 media supplemented with 10 % and 20 % foetal bovine serum (FBS), respectively (Biowest, Nuaille, France), and MDCK II BCRP cells were cultured in DMEM (Biowest, Nuaille, France) supplemented with 10 % FBS. All cell lines were additionally supplemented with streptomycin (50 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$), penicillin G (50 U/mL), and *l*-glutamine (2 mM), all delivered by Biowest, Nuaille, France. The cell lines were stored under liquid nitrogen [media/DMSO (90 %/10 %)]. Cultivation conditions: $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5 % CO_2 -humidified atmosphere. Cells were detached for sub-culturing or biological assessment applying a trypsin-EDTA solution (0.05 %/0.02 %; Biowest, Nuaille, France) at a confluence of $\sim 90\%$. The cells were centrifuged and washed with fresh cell culture media. Cell counting was performed with a Scepter handheld automated cell counter (60 μM capillary sensor; EMD Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA).

2.2.4. Functional analyses

The calcein AM (ABCB1 and ABCC1) [22,23,25,33,34,38,56–58], daunorubicin (ABCB1 and ABCC1) [22,23,33,34,56,57], Hoechst 33342 (ABCB1 and ABCG2) [22,23], and pheophorbide A (ABCG2) [22,23,25,33,34,38,56] assays were conducted as reported earlier. Dilution series of compounds **17–22** covering a concentration range between 1000 μM and 1 μM were prepared and 20 μL were transferred onto clear (calcein AM, daunorubicin, and pheophorbide A) or black (Hoechst 33342) 96-well flat-bottom plates (Brand, Wertheim, Germany), followed by addition of 160 μL cell suspension [plate reader assays (calcein AM and Hoechst 33342): 30,000 cells/well; flow cytometer assays (daunorubicin and pheophorbide A): 45,000 cells/well] in either phenol red-free RPMI-1640 (A2780/ADR and H69AR) or phenol red-free DMEM (MDCK II BCRP) without further supplements. An incubation period of 30 min at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5 % CO_2 -humidified atmosphere followed in case of calcein AM and Hoechst 33342 assays. Subsequently, 20 μL fluorescence dye (calcein AM: 3.125 μM ; daunorubicin: 30 μM ; Hoechst 33342: 10 μM ; and pheophorbide A: 5 μM) was added to each well. Either the fluorescence increase was measured over a time period of 30 min (calcein AM; excitation: 485 nm; emission: 520 nm) or 120 min (Hoechst 33342; excitation: 360 nm; emission: 460 nm) in 30 s intervals applying a Paradigm microplate reader (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA), or the average fluorescence value per well was determined after incubation of 180 min (daunorubicin) or 120 min (pheophorbide A) applying an Attune NxT flow cytometer (Invitrogen, Waltham, MA, USA; excitation: 488 nm; emission: 695/50 nm). Slopes from the linear fluorescence increase (calcein AM) or the average steady state fluorescence value per well (daunorubicin, Hoechst 33342, and pheophorbide A) were calculated and compared to the standard inhibitors. Data processing including determination of IC_{50} values was accomplished using GraphPad Prism version 8.4.0.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Bioactivity–physicochemistry linear regression analysis

3.1.1. Bioactivity and physicochemistry data processing

The plots between bioactivity and CLogP (**Supplementary Fig. 1**), MW (**Supplementary Fig. 2**), MR (**Supplementary Fig. 3**), and TPSA (**Supplementary Fig. 4**) of the 88, 61, and 409 selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibitors, respectively, as well as the 187 focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors (D–F) of the ABC_BPMDS show that the data is well distributed along the bioactivity-physicochemistry space, and no clear correlation could be deduced from these plots. Hence, bioactivity as well as physicochemistry values were combined according to the sub-classification of compounds as described in [Section 2.1.1](#). For this purpose, mean as well as SEM values were calculated.

3.1.2. Bidirectional one-phase linear regression analysis

One-phase linear regressions are most popular in terms of correlations between bioactivity and physicochemistry of ABC transporter inhibitors [39,40,42,56]. Hence, the calculated mean and SEM values of both bioactivity and CLogP (**Supplementary Fig. 5**), MW (**Supplementary Fig. 6**), MR (**Supplementary Fig. 7**), and TPSA (**Supplementary Fig. 8**) of the 88, 61, and 409 selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibitors, respectively, of the ABC_BPMDS were plotted and a linear regression was conducted in a bidirectional fashion. Except for CLogP (ABCC1 and ABCG2) and TPSA (ABCG2), all physicochemical properties seem to stand in a clear linear correlation to the bioactivity Sub-Classes. However, the correlations between bioactivity and CLogP (**Supplementary Fig. 9**), MW (**Supplementary Fig. 10**), MR (**Supplementary Fig. 11**), and TPSA (**Supplementary Fig. 12**) of the 117 sub-classified focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors (A–C) of the ABC_BPMDS did not follow these correlations as demonstrated by strong deviations particularly at low bioactivity values (Weak and Very Weak Class 7 compounds). These deviations in physicochemistry indicated sub-populations of compounds that were not properly reflected in one unified bioactivity-physicochemistry pair value. Since a bidirectional approach does generally not acknowledge the existence of a global optimum including a potential decline in bioactivity after exceeding this optimum, and the strong deviations particularly at low bioactivity values indicated the existence of optima values, we were prompted to establish a multidirectional two-phase linear regression.

3.1.3. Multidirectional two-phase linear regression analysis

In order to provide advanced insights into the bioactivity-physicochemistry relationships, we conducted a multidirectional two-phase linear regression analysis assuming one global optimum. The mean value of the highest Sub-class was taken as reference value and fix-point for the two regression lines. In addition, the reference value was also used to divide the compounds of the following Sub-classes into two sub-populations. A bidirectional one-phase linear regression was conducted for each of the sub-populations using the reference value as fix-point. The resultant triangle indicated by the two regression lines is an indicator of the bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape of the respective Class. [Table 1](#) reflects the determined reference values (optima values for mathematical operations), peak values [Sub-Class with actual highest bioactivity (top value)], and ranges (range of physicochemistry values defined by the Sub-Classes with lowest and highest average physicochemistry values) of selective and focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors.

3.2. In-depth physicochemistry evaluation

3.2.1. Calculated octanol/water coefficient (CLogP)

CLogP is a surrogate parameter for compound lipophilicity which has frequently been used in virtual screening approaches as discriminator to select the molecules of interest [22,23,25,38]. Lipophilicity is an

Table 1

Summary of the metrical values determined by the multidirectional two-phase linear regression analysis. Reference value: optimum value for the respective Class; peak value: actual highest bioactivity value.

	ABCB1	ABCC1	ABCG2
CLogP range (reference/peak value)			
Selective inhibitors	3.54–7.90 (6.91/6.91)	1.98–4.80 (3.45/3.45)	2.73–6.26 (4.68/4.68)
Multitarget inhibitors	2.47–5.16 (4.25/4.25)	2.47–5.16 (4.25/4.25)	2.47–5.16 (4.25/4.25)
MW range (reference/peak value)			
Selective inhibitors	357.80–808.95 (684.83/684.83)	310.39–449.18 (396.95/396.95)	301.95–509.86 (425.00/425.00)
Multitarget inhibitors	376.57–689.28 (480.01/653.94)	376.57–689.28 (480.01/480.01)	376.57–689.28 (480.01/376.57)
MR range (reference/peak value)			
Selective inhibitors	10.32–20.51 (18.89/18.89)	9.01–12.69 (11.70/11.70)	8.77–13.91 (11.54/11.54)
Multitarget inhibitors	10.73–22.08 (13.53/17.89)	10.73–22.08 (13.53/13.53)	10.73–22.08 (13.53/10.73)
TPSA range (reference/peak value)			
Selective inhibitors	48.00–163.74 (102.45/102.45)	55.08–97.78 (68.81/68.81)	59.95–126.65 (103.40/103.40)
Multitarget inhibitors	58.23–194.09 (89.40/137.66)	58.23–194.09 (89.40/89.40)	58.23–194.09 (89.40/62.28)

important characteristic of drugs as it critically impacts the ADME model, and thus, influences CNS penetration in a way that low CLogP values impede CNS penetration [50–52]. Particularly, CLogP is a well-established descriptor for ABCB1 inhibition [39], efficacy [41], activation [40], and affinity [42]. Several reports have demonstrated the linearity between bioactivity of molecules and their CLogP [39–42,56]. This linearity followed an upward trajectory, outlining the most potent and affine compounds as very lipophilic [39–42,56]. However, these analyses included only a very limited number of analyzed molecules and only one particular pharmacological target [39–42,56]. No correlation has been carried out for more than one pharmacological target [39–42]. Similar one-target correlations are known in terms of ABCC1 [56] and ABCG2 [56], however, these correlations were always compound (sub) class specific and no general conclusions could be drawn for drug discovery and development [56]. Particularly for ABCC1, low CNS penetration of drugs was pinned to low CLogP values [52].

As can be seen from [Fig. 3](#), the physicochemical profile in terms of CLogP of selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibitors varies drastically. While very potent selective ABCB1 inhibitors have an unusually high lipophilicity, selective ABCC1 and ABCG2 inhibitors have much smaller spans at substantially lower values. Our multidirectional two-phase linear regression analysis revealed that CLogP is a very distinctive descriptor for selective ABC transporter inhibition of well-studied ABC transporters. The strong correlation between CLogP and ABCB1 inhibition has been demonstrated for individual compound classes before [39–42,56], and this confirmed reproducibility with the data collected in the data set demonstrates the applicability domain of the ABC_BPMDS.

Furthermore, [Fig. 3](#) shows the correlations of focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors with respect to ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibition. As can be visualized, the bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape seems to be a compromise of the distinct preferences of the individual transporters. This is particularly reflected in a strongly reduced span in terms of ABCB1 inhibition, while ABCC1 and ABCG2 inhibition seemed to stretch into a larger CLogP span compared to selective ABCC1 and ABCG2 inhibitors. Interestingly, the CLogP values of Medium and Semi Class 7 molecules seem to be slightly shifted into the direction of the bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape

Fig. 3. Bioactivity-CLogP plots of the 88, 61, and 409 selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibitors, respectively, as well as the 117 sub-classified focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors against ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F). Outstanding, Extraordinary, Superior, Medium, Semi, Weak, and Very Weak Class 1 (A)/2 (B)/3 (C)/7 (D–F) compounds are depicted as magenta, violet, blue, green, yellow, orange, and red closed squares, respectively. Class 0 compounds are shown as solid black circles and the bioactivity value has been determined to be 2.699 (arbitrary value of 2000 μM according to the ABC_BPMDS [21]). Outliers are defined as single data points pair, and are shown as open squares. The correlations are depicted as black lines. The multidirectional two-phase linear correlations of selective ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibitors are depicted with grey closed circles and grey lines for comparison reasons (outliers: grey open circles). The CLogP ranges of selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) as well as pan-ABC transporter (D–F) inhibitors are indicated with black dashed lines, and the ranges of selective ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibitors are depicted with grey dashed lines for comparison reasons. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

of the respective selective ABC transporter inhibitors. This finding stresses the notion that the span of CLogP of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors is largely defined by a compromise rather than by a peculiar characteristic to serve the individual preferences of the respective transporter. However, as the distinct preferences of the transporters run inversely proportional (Fig. 3A–C), a compromise cannot serve these preferences optimally. This conclusion explains the limitations with respect to potent pan-ABC transporter inhibition. Thus, only a very limited number of potent pan-ABC transporter inhibitors of ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 beyond the 5 μM threshold value is known.

To confirm the found boundaries of bioactivity, the average values of the 114 Class 0 compounds were also plotted after splitting this compound set into two sub-populations according to the respective reference CLogP values of selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors as well as focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors of ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2. Strikingly, in all cases, the boundaries between bioactivity and bioinactivity as determined by the multidirectional two-phase linear correlations could be reproduced, which strongly underlines the found results.

3.2.2. Molecular weight (MW)

Besides CLogP, MW is a popular descriptor of bioactivity of ABC transporter inhibitors which has been used in computational approaches as screening filter to extract the molecules of interest [23]. And similar to CLogP, a bidirectional correlation has been observed particularly for ABCB1 inhibition [42,56], efficacy [41], and ABCB1 substrate recognition [43,44], demonstrating that heavy molecules are most potent [42], effective [41], and affine [44]. However, these analyses were performed without correlations to additional ABC transporters [44]. In terms of ABCC1 [56,57] and ABCG2 [56], our group has demonstrated earlier a (non-)linear correlation between MW and inhibition by the compound class of pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines. MW was discovered as a particularly important factor for CNS penetration in a way that larger molecules permeate to a lesser extent into the CNS [44,50,51]. This has

implications for the design of future anti-AD drugs targeting ABC transporters.

Fig. 4 outlines the ranges of MW in terms of selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibition, which is very similar to the correlations demonstrated in Fig. 3A–C with respect to CLogP. The span of MW values within selective ABCB1 inhibitors stretches much broader compared to selective ABCC1 and ABCG2 inhibitors. Particularly, selective ABCC1 inhibition seems to take place in a very narrow band between ~ 300 and 450 g/mol, which is a considerable limitation compared to the overall span of the compounds in the ABC_BPMDS (~ 150 –1300). Strikingly, the bioactivity boundaries of selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors are flanked by the two sub-population average values of the 114 Class 0 compounds, which was already demonstrated for the correlations between bioactivity and CLogP. These findings underline the clear distinction between bioactivity and bioinactivity.

In addition, Fig. 4 shows the correlations of focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors with respect to ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), as well as ABCG2 (F) inhibition and MW. As it has already been demonstrated for CLogP, the bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape forms a compromise between the individual transporters. This is again reflected in a reduced span of MW regarding ABCB1 inhibition, while the bioactivity against ABCC1 and ABCG2 seemed generally to be shifted toward molecules of higher MW compared to selective ABCC1 and ABCG2 inhibitors. This becomes evident considering that the molecules have to provide additional space for necessary substructural features to address the distinct transporters' preferences. The likelihood to find these substructural features is increased in molecules of higher MW.

Strikingly, the observation of biochemistry-physicochemistry shifts of the Medium and Semi Class 7 compounds toward the bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape of selective inhibitors is even more pronounced. This discovery supports the hypothesis that focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors form a compromise in terms of individual transporter preferences. The considerably different optima in MW which

Fig. 4. Bioactivity-MW plots of the 88, 61, and 409 selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibitors, respectively, as well as the 117 sub-classified focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors against ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F). Outstanding, Extraordinary, Superior, Medium, Semi, Weak, and Very Weak Class 1 (A)/2 (B)/3 (C)/7 (D–F) compounds are depicted as magenta, violet, blue, green, yellow, orange, and red closed squares, respectively. Class 0 compounds are shown as solid black circles and the bioactivity value has been determined to be 2.699 (arbitrary value of 2000 μM according to the ABC_BPMDS [21]). Outliers are defined as single data points pair, and are shown as open squares. The correlations are depicted as black lines. The multidirectional two-phase linear correlations of selective ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibitors are depicted with grey closed circles and grey lines for comparison reasons (outliers: grey open circles). The MW ranges of selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) as well as pan-ABC transporter (D–F) inhibitors are indicated with black dashed lines, and the ranges of selective ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibitors are depicted with grey dashed lines for comparison reasons. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Bioactivity-MR plots of the 88, 61, and 409 selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibitors, respectively, as well as the 117 sub-classified focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors against ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F). Outstanding, Extraordinary, Superior, Medium, Semi, Weak, and Very Weak Class 1 (A)/2 (B)/3 (C)/7 (D–F) compounds are depicted as magenta, violet, blue, green, yellow, orange, and red closed squares, respectively. Class 0 compounds are shown as solid black circles and the bioactivity value has been determined to be 2.699 (arbitrary value of 2000 μM according to the ABC_BPMDS [21]). Outliers are defined as single data points pair, and are shown as open squares. The correlations are depicted as black lines. The multidirectional two-phase linear correlations of selective ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibitors are depicted with grey closed circles and grey lines for comparison reasons (outliers: grey open circles). The MR ranges of selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) as well as pan-ABC transporter (D–F) inhibitors are indicated with black dashed lines, and the ranges of selective ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibitors are depicted with grey dashed lines for comparison reasons. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

determine the bioactivities against ABCB1 on the one side and ABCC1 as well as ABCG2 on the other side limit the overall potency of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors.

Interestingly, compared to the correlations between CLogP and bioactivity of sub-classified Class 7 compounds (Fig. 3D–F), the higher sub-population value of the 114 Class 0 molecules did not exactly match the found bioactivity boundaries, while the lower value matched perfectly in terms of ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibition. The upper value appeared at lower MW values than could be expected from the multidirectional two-phase correlations. This effect could be explained by the fact that MW spans are narrower at the lower end of the MW scale, and thus, average values are less prone to data variation as the upper end, where individual molecules with extreme MW values may occur in sub-classes containing a low quantity of compounds.

3.2.3. Molar refractivity (MR)

MR is a measure of the tendency of a mole of a compound to obtain a dipole moment under exposure to an electric field (polarizability). It was analyzed with respect to efficacy against ABCB1-overexpressing cells [41] and its importance with respect to ABCB1 substrate recognition has been acknowledged [59]. However, the usage of MR as descriptor is rather unpopular and is generally overlooked in virtual screening approaches.

Fig. 5 highlights the ranges of the MR in terms of selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibitors, which resemble the ranges given in Fig. 4A–C in terms of the MW of selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors. While the overall span of selective ABCB1 inhibitors is very large (~10–21), the spans of selective ABCC1 and ABCG2 inhibitors largely overlap and are much narrower compared to selective ABCB1 inhibitors.

As already demonstrated for the correlations between bioactivity and CLogP as well as MW, the bioactivity boundaries of selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors clearly overlap with the two sub-population values of the 114 Class 0 compounds, supporting the existence of the boundaries between bioactivity and bioinactivity.

Furthermore, Fig. 5 shows the correlations of focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors regarding ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibition. In contrast to the CLogP correlations, the MR span of focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors is very large and, surprisingly, exceeds even the large span of selective ABCB1 inhibitors at the upper end of the MR space. This tendency was already observed for the bioactivity-MW correlation as outlined in Fig. 4D–F, however, is more pronounced in terms of MR. One explanation could be that the comparably large molecules which contain the necessary substructural features to serve the individual preferences of the transporters pose a higher tendency to be polarized. These substructural features include heteroatoms with increased electronegativity, and hence, polarizability of the entire substructure to form an electric dipole moment. Additionally, as already outlined for CLogP and particularly MW, the shift of Medium and Semi Class 7 values is very pronounced, underlining the notion that focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors form a physicochemical compromise in terms of their bioactivity against three different targets.

As already demonstrated for the correlations between the bioactivity of sub-classified Class 7 compounds and MW, the higher sub-population value of the 114 Class 0 molecules did also not match the identified bioactivity-MR boundaries at the upper end of the MR space, as it appeared at lower MR values than could be expected from the multidirectional two-phase correlations. As MR values are finite at the lower end of the scale (comparable to MW and different from CLogP), the larger deviations may be caused by extreme molecules which exist amongst the ABC_BPMDS, particularly Class 7 compounds, that caused this large expansion to upper MR values.

3.2.4. Topological polar surface area (TPSA)

TPSA is a measure of the polarity of the surface of a compound taking particularly polar heavy atoms into account. TPSA is less famous with

respect to ABC transporters than CLogP or MW, however, was demonstrated to correlate with bioactivity, specifically, activation of the ABCB1 ATPase [40], ABCB1 substrate recognition [43], and ABCC1 affinity [45], outlining compounds with higher polar surface area to be tendentially more active [40] and affine [45]. However, only a very minor number of compounds was taken into account in these analyses [40,45], and no cross-correlation to other pharmacological targets was undertaken [40,43,45]. Nevertheless, TPSA is a particularly important physicochemical property in terms of CNS penetration of drugs in a way that increased polar surface impedes CNS penetration [50–52], which has large implications for anti-AD therapeutics as well.

Fig. 6 provides the detailed analysis of selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), as well as ABCG2 (C) inhibitors with respect to TPSA. Although the span of selective ABCB1 inhibitors is broader compared to selective ABCC1 and ABCG2 inhibitors, it is much narrower compared to the other physicochemical properties CLogP, MW, and MR. Generally, the bioactivity space of selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors seems to cover a range between ~60 and 100 Å, and a large overlap between these three Classes exists, revealing MR as rather indistinctive compared to the other physicochemical properties. Particularly the results of Fig. 6B are supported by findings that ABCC1 substrates are located within the outlined TPSA band, limiting their CNS penetration due to ABCC1-mediated efflux [52]. In contrast to the CLogP (Fig. 3A), MW (Fig. 4A), and MR correlations (Fig. 5A), the sub-population average values of the 114 Class 0 compounds did not exactly flank the found boundaries of the multidirectional two-phase correlations between ABCB1 bioactivity and TPSA as these values appeared at the inner ends of the boundaries. However, perfect matches were observed for selective ABCC1 (Fig. 5B) and ABCG2 (Fig. 5C) inhibitors.

Moreover, Fig. 6 shows the correlations of focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors regarding ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibition. As already observed for MR (Fig. 5A–C), the TPSA span of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors is larger than the spans of selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors and even exceeds the large span of selective ABCB1 inhibitors at the upper end of the TPSA space. TPSA depends on the number and manner of electronegative heavy atoms, particularly nitrogen and oxygen, and many of the necessary substructural features of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors contain such heavy atoms to serve the individual preferences of the transporters. These multitarget agents have an increased tendency to have a higher polar surface area. In addition, as already outlined for the other physicochemical properties CLogP, MW, and MR, the shift of Medium and Semi Class 7 values is very pronounced. This finding supports the hypothesis that pan-ABC transporter inhibitors form a compromise in terms of physicochemistry, and hence, are not able to optimally address the individual transporters' preferences, resulting in a very limited number of compounds exceeding the 5 µM limit.

A tighter limit of the higher sub-population average value of the 114 Class 0 compounds was also observed for the TPSA correlations, which aligns well with our findings for the MW and MR correlations. As TPSA is a measure that does not allow for negative values (compared to CLogP), the mean values of sub-classes particularly at the upper end of the TPSA scale are prone to larger deviations, which is also the case with respect to MW and MR. On the other hand, the lower sub-population average value matched perfectly with the found boundaries (Fig. 6D–F).

3.3. Validation of results

3.3.1. Plotting of unclassified Class 7 compounds

By sub-classifying Class 7 molecules according to a rule scheme as defined earlier [22] and as outlined in Fig. 2F, 70 molecules could not be classified. These unclassified Class 7 molecules represent a suitable validation data set to confirm the found interrelationships between bioactivity and physicochemistry. Thus, we plotted the individual bioactivity-physicochemistry value pairs and compared them with the found multidirectional two-phase correlations of focused pan-ABC

Fig. 6. Bioactivity-TPSA plots of the 88, 61, and 409 selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) inhibitors, respectively, as well as the 117 sub-classified focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors against ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F). Outstanding, Extraordinary, Superior, Medium, Semi, Weak, and Very Weak Class 1 (A)/2 (B)/3 (C)/7 (D–F) compounds are depicted as magenta, violet, blue, green, yellow, orange, and red closed squares, respectively. Class 0 compounds are shown as solid black circles and the bioactivity value has been determined to be 2.699 (arbitrary value of 2000 μ M according to the ABC_BPMDS [21]). Outliers are defined as single data points pair, and are shown as open squares. The correlations are depicted as black lines. The multidirectional two-phase linear correlations of selective ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibitors are depicted with grey closed circles and grey lines for comparison reasons (outliers: grey open circles). The TPSA ranges of selective ABCB1 (A), ABCC1 (B), and ABCG2 (C) as well as pan-ABC transporter (D–F) inhibitors are indicated with black dashed lines, and the ranges of selective ABCB1 (D), ABCC1 (E), and ABCG2 (F) inhibitors are depicted with grey dashed lines for comparison reasons. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

transporter inhibitors. As can be seen in **Supplementary Figs. 13–16**, most individual value pairs of the 70 unclassified compounds lied around the correlation lines or within the bioactivity-physicochemistry triangle with rare outliers outside of the correlations. Particularly, most data points accumulated around the upward trajectory part of the multidirectional two-phase correlations. However, the data points are generally spread within the bioactivity-physicochemistry space. To obtain a less foggy picture, we applied the same sub-classification in terms of ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibition as used for selective inhibitors, and the reference values were used which were already applied in **Figs. 3–6** for focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors. **Fig. 7** shows the bioactivity-physicochemistry plots against ABCB1 (A, D, G, and J), ABCC1 (B, E, H, and K), and ABCG2 (C, F, I, and L) with respect to CLogP (A, B, and C), MW (D, E, and F), MR (G, H, and I), and TPSA (J, K, and L). As can be seen from all plots, the majority of value pairs followed the trajectory of the multidirectional two-phase correlations. Additionally, the tendency of classified potent focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors to shift to the physicochemistry optima of selective inhibitors can also be recognized for the 70 unclassified Class 7 compounds. These observations strongly support the findings of our study.

3.3.2. Biological assessment of novel pan-ABC transporter inhibitors

In order to further validate the found results we sought to analyze the discovered parameter optima and spans with respect to focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors of ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 that are not part of the ABC_BPMDS. We identified 6 novel molecules in our compound library which contain also substructural features of known ABC transporter activators, particularly 1,2,4-oxadiazole (compounds 17–18), phenothiazine (compounds 19–20), purine (compound 20), pyrrolo [3,2-*d*]pyrimidine (compound 21), and thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (compound 22). **Fig. 8** shows the evaluated molecules. These specific substructural features of compounds 17–22 give focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors a special relevance in the development of novel activators of ABC transporters as already outlined in our previous work

[24]. **Table 2** provides the summarized inhibitory activities of compounds 17–22 including their associated physicochemical properties, while **Supplementary Table 1** provides the bioactivity data of the individually used functional assays.

Fig. 9 shows the bioactivity-physicochemistry plots against ABCB1 (A, D, G, and J), ABCC1 (B, E, H, and K), and ABCG2 (C, F, I, and L) with respect to the physicochemical properties CLogP (A, B, and C), MW (D, E, and F), MR (G, H, and I), and TPSA (J, K, and L). Regarding CLogP, compounds 20–22 follow the upward trajectory correlation with respect to ABCB1 and ABCC1 inhibition. In addition, compound 17 also falls within the correlation in terms of ABCC1 inhibition, while it falls out of the correlation concerning ABCB1. On the other hand, none of the compounds seem to follow the correlation regarding ABCG2 inhibition (except for compound 21), however, all compounds present well within the bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape of focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors. Concerning MW, MR, and TPSA, most compounds followed the upward trajectory part of the multidirectional two-phase linear regression lines, which is particularly true for the ABCC1 correlations. The only exceptions with respect to all transporters were compounds 19 (MW, MR, and TPSA) and 21 (MR). Considering that compounds 17–22 provide individual data points that are prone to lie outside of averaged data points, as this is the case for the individual Sub-classes, the accuracy of the correlations in terms of the outlined bioactivity-physicochemistry landscapes is remarkable. In addition, compound 19 contains a phenothiazine moiety, which is not represented in both the set of 187 focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors (0 molecules) and the entire ABC_BPMDS (0 molecules). This fact implies on the one hand that no information in terms of the bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape is known for this particular compound class, specifically with respect to the polypharmacological landscape. On the other hand, this gap between compound 19 and the found correlations as outlined in **Figs. 3–6** leaves enough exploratory space for the discovery of uncharted landscapes for the development of innovative bioactive molecules.

Fig. 7. Bioactivity-physicochemistry plots of the 70 unclassified focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors (black closed circles) of ABCB1 (A, D, G, and J), ABCB1 (B, E, H, and K), and ABCG2 (C, F, I, and L) with respect to CLogP (A, B, and C), MW (D, E, and F), MR (G, H, and I), as well as TPSA (J, K, and L) compared to the multidirectional two-phase linear correlations of classified Class 7 compounds (grey closed circles and grey lines). The 70 molecules were sub-classified according to the rule scheme for selective inhibitors as outlined in Fig. 2 F and were subsequently sub-divided into two sub-populations using the respective reference values of focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors as outlined in Table 1. Outliers are defined as single bioactivity-physicochemistry value pairs and are shown as open circles.

4. Conclusions

4.1. Applicability domain of the ABC_{BPMDS}

One major finding of this study is the reproducibility of previous reports which included mostly only a very minor number of analyzed compounds [39–45,56]. By using a comprehensive dataset that describes the entire bioactivity landscape of the well-studied ABC transporters ABCB1, ABCB1, and ABCG2 (ABC_{BPMDS}; www.panabc.info) [21,54,55], bidirectional one-phase linear regression analyses revealed similar results as reported earlier (Supplementary Figs. 5–8) [39–45,56]. These findings demonstrate the applicability domain of the ABC_{BPMDS} and its potential regarding expansion into other descriptor fields. Furthermore, the reproducibility underlined the usefulness of physicochemistry as additional discriminator to filter for bioactive

compounds – which may support future drug discovery approaches (i) to downsize ultra-large compound libraries, e.g., the steadily growing Enamine *REAL SPACE* compound library; (ii) to enhance the prediction rate in drug discovery approaches; (iii) to promote further decision making in the process of drug design; or (iv) to develop an entirely physicochemistry-based prediction model for the discovery of bioactive molecules.

In addition, the present work expanded the applicability domain of the bioactivity space of the well-studied ABC transporters ABCB1, ABCB1, and ABCG2 by correlating the entirely known bioactivity landscapes of the transporters to each other. This expansion included on the one hand the analysis of focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors, but also the analysis of truly selective agents – which opposes the classical approaches of the past which, without exception, focused only one particular target, and thus, were not able to differentiate between truly

Fig. 8. Depiction of biologically evaluated pan-ABC transporter inhibitors including their substructural features (red) relevant in terms of ABC transporter activation. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

Bioactivity values expressed as $IC_{50} \pm SEM$ of biologically evaluated focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors 17–22 determined in different functional assays and cell lines as outlined in **Supplementary Table 1**.

Compd.	Substructural Feature	ABCB1 $IC_{50} \pm SEM$ [μM] ($pIC_{50} \pm SEM$)	ABCC1 $IC_{50} \pm SEM$ [μM] ($pIC_{50} \pm SEM$)	ABCG2 $IC_{50} \pm SEM$ [μM] ($pIC_{50} \pm SEM$)	CLogP	MW	MR	TPSA
17	1,2,4-Oxadiazole	117 ± 9 (3.933 ± 0.051)	25.8 ± 4.2 (4.607 ± 0.108)	105 ± 10 (3.984 ± 0.064)	3.63	394.52	11.2	55.05
18	1,2,4-Oxadiazole	27.8 ± 1.6 (4.558 ± 0.039)	22.3 ± 4.3 (4.675 ± 0.125)	47.1 ± 9.7 (4.354 ± 0.134)	4.00	398.88	10.6	80.83
19	Phenothiazine	31.3 ± 6.5 (4.550 ± 0.135)	48.5 ± 7.8 (4.347 ± 0.105)	46.2 ± 7.5 (4.369 ± 0.106)	4.63	241.36	7.45	3.24
20	Phenothiazine/Purine	9.72 ± 3.10 (5.055 ± 0.205)	11.5 ± 2.9 (4.968 ± 0.163)	16.7 ± 3.9 (4.800 ± 0.152)	3.66	437.57	12.0	74.77
21	Pyrrolo[3,2- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine	22.9 ± 3.4 (4.650 ± 0.097)	18.7 ± 12.8 (4.893 ± 0.407)	13.8 ± 0.9 (4.864 ± 0.042)	3.26	383.68	8.74	54.04
22	Thieno[2,3- <i>d</i>]pyrimidine	43.9 ± 12.8 (4.411 ± 0.188)	21.2 ± 5.2 (4.724 ± 0.158)	59.1 ± 17.7 (4.303 ± 0.193)	3.46	404.52	11.5	75.62

selective and non-selective agents [39–45,56]. Strikingly, the conducted multidirectional two-phase linear regression analyses (Figs. 3–6) also confirmed previous findings [39–45,56], however, at the same time, outlined that former analyses were insufficient in terms of the bioactivity-physicochemistry correlations of bioactive ABC transporter inhibitors, given the fact that optima values exist.

4.2. Potential role of underrepresented physicochemical properties

The present work provided a major understanding with respect to the bioactivity-physicochemistry connectivity network of famous physicochemical properties. In contrast to CLogP and MW [39–44,56,57], analyses regarding MR and TPSA are clearly underrepresented in the literature [41,59], particularly in terms of virtual screening approaches.

The present report expands into this gap by analyses of both, selective and multitarget agents, with respect to MR and TPSA. These analyses outlined a niche beyond the known bioactivity-physicochemistry landscape of selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors in which solely multitargeting of ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 exists (Figs. 5D–F and 6D–F). Although this niche included only Weak and Very Weak Class 7 compounds, it leaves enough exploratory potential for the future design of novel multitarget agents which may be refined in terms of their potency and general pharmacological profile with targeted synthesis approaches. Deciphering the interconnection between manner and value of physicochemical properties and their differential impact on ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibition (promiscuity vs selectivity) will provide potential drug candidates for biological assessment against other, less- and under-studied ABC transporters, exploring their nature, function, as

Fig. 9. Bioactivity-physicochemistry plots of the 117 sub-classified focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors of ABCB1 (A, D, G, and J), ABCB1 (B, E, H, and K), and ABCG2 (C, F, I, and L) with respect to CLogP (A, B, and C), MW (D, E, and F), MR (G, H, and I), as well as TPSA (J, K, and L). The multidirectional two-phase linear correlations are depicted with grey closed circles (outliers: open circles) and grey lines which are compared to compounds 17 (black open circles), 18 (black upward open triangles), 19 (black downward open triangles), 20 (black open routes), 21 (black open squares), and 22 (black open hexagons).

well as their suitability as therapeutic or diagnostic pharmacological drug targets of the future.

4.3. Physicochemistry and the multitarget binding site

One major outcome of the present study is the finding that pan-ABC transporter inhibitors found a compromise of the distinct preferences of the individual transporters as indicated by the plots of selective ABCB1 (Figs. 3–6A), ABCB1 (Figs. 3–6B), and ABCG2 (Figs. 3–6C) inhibitors, as well as focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors regarding ABCB1 (Figs. 3–6D), ABCB1 (Figs. 3–6E), and ABCG2 (Figs. 3–6F) inhibition. This has large implications for the recently proposed multitarget binding site of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors amongst all/most ABC transport proteins [22–26]. This multitarget binding site is believed to consist of common or mutually overlapping amino acid sequences and structural motifs beyond the highly conserved nucleotide-binding domains (NBDs)

[23,25,26]. Particularly the differentiation between ‘common’ and ‘mutually overlapping’ is addressed by the findings of the present study. As focused pan-ABC transporter inhibitors seem to form a compromise to serve the individual transporters’ preferences, the multitarget binding site appears to be built by individual but largely overlapping binding sites within the membrane-spanning domains (MSDs) of ABC transporters, which is supported by five aspects:

- (i) A very recent first-in-field study applying a blind docking approach with cross-validation using a set of 23 potent focused and truly multitarget pan-ABC transporter inhibitors outlined a common binding region and orientation of most of these compounds within the MSDs of the under-studied ABC transporter ABCA7 [24];
- (ii) The available structural data of ABC transporters [cryogenic electron microscopy (cryo-EM) or homology modelling]

indicated primary binding sites of ligands of various well-, less-, and under-studied ABC transporters that were in the vast majority of cases within the MSDs in regions comparable to the discovered multitarget binding site of ABCA7. This was the case, for example, for ABCB1 [60,61], ABCB2 [62,63], ABCB4 [64], ABCB5 [65], ABCC1 [66], ABCC4 [67], ABCC5 [68], ABCC6 [69], ABCC7 [70], ABCC8 [71], ABCC11 [72], and ABCG2 [58,73];

- (iii) The additional, adjacent, individual, non-related, non-overlapping (=distinct) parts of the mutually overlapping multitarget binding site may be the main discriminators between potent and weak pan-ABC transporter inhibition, and thus, represent the peculiar part of the commonly shared mutually overlapping multitarget binding site that defines favorability of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors [24]. Hence, strong binding affinities may result for compounds that contain additional substructural features that address these distinct additional sub-binding sites, while weaker affinities could be caused by molecules that contain only the ‘basic requirements’ for multitarget inhibition [24];
- (iv) These distinct parts of the mutually overlapping multitarget binding site could be the reason why physicochemistry-shifts were observed deviating from the multidirectional two-phase correlations (Figs. 3–6D–F and 7A–L) outlining that potent pan-ABC transporter inhibitors have a physicochemistry which resembles selective and potent inhibitors;
- (v) The limitations with respect to potent pan-ABC transporter inhibitors with IC₅₀ values that barely reach below the 5 μM threshold can be explained by the distinct parts of the mutually overlapping multitarget binding site which require opposing physicochemical properties, particularly in terms of CLogP (Fig. 3A–C), MW (Fig. 4A–C), and MR (Fig. 5A–C). Optimum values for these physicochemical properties exist for selective ABCB1, ABCC1, and ABCG2 inhibitors, and their inverse correlation limits the overall potency of pan-ABC transporter inhibitors.

In conclusion, these mutually overlapping sequences and motifs indicate a conserved functional similarity within the ABC transporter superfamily which may be harnessed for future drug design and development, particularly focusing under-studied ABC transporters that

cannot be addressed by small-molecules until today, also in terms of AD [23,25,26]. Fig. 10 visualizes the perception of the multitarget binding site.

4.4. Outlook: pan-ABC transporter inhibitors in AD and other diseases

Pan-ABC transporter inhibitors inhere a great potential to address less- and under-studied ABC transporters, for example, ABCA1 and ABCA7, which were both associated to AD [1]. Strikingly, many pan-ABC transporter inhibitors contain conserved substructural features such as (non-)aromatic poly(hetero)cycles and functional groups that can also be found in activators of ABC transporters [21,23,27–38]. Additionally, several compound classes of the same series comprised of both inhibitors and activators [33,36]. Particularly, their analysis for CLogP, MW, MR and TPSA is of high relevance as these physicochemical parameters contribute to CNS penetration [44,50–52], and the CNS represents the major venue of anti-AD drugs.

Taken together, these compound classes and conserved substructural elements may serve as templates and transition molecules for the targeted development of ABC transporter activators (i) for drug development and (ii) as *in vitro* tools for research. However, it must be considered that multitarget ABC transporter inhibitors and the subsequent targeted development of activators represent only the first of numerous steps to specific AD therapeutics. Particularly, the multitarget nature of these molecules needs to be abandoned in subsequent organic synthesis approaches to (i) prevent a general, systemic activation of ABC transporters in the entire human body, and (ii) to circumvent pharmacokinetic constraints by recognition of these molecules by other efflux transporters at the BBB, and thus, enabling them to reach their destination (particularly in the case of ABCA1 and ABCA7). Nevertheless, pan-ABC transporter modulators may be harnessed to address AD-associated less- and under-studied ABC transporters to promote the extrusion and/or degradation of Aβ from the human brain. Thus, ABC transporters may be explored as pharmacological AD targets of the future, potentially preventing or at least ameliorating AD development and/or progression.

Finally, it must be considered that the statistical framework set by the ABC_BPMDs including the comprehensive analyses as described in the present work has large implications for virtual screening approaches. Our results indicate that the physicochemical properties possibly aid to

Fig. 10. Perception of the multitarget binding site and adjacent non-overlapping individual binding sites of AD-relevant transporters.

shape the polypharmacological profile of the drug of the future. This holds not only true with respect to human ABC transporters, but also regarding other (under-studied) protein families, such as bacterial ABC transporters, GPCRs, ICs, SLCs (PANSLC; www.panslc.info), or tyrosine kinases (TKs) – providing a great potential to treat yet incurable diseases.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vigneshwaran Namasivayam: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Katja Stefan:** Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Lukas Gorecki:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Jan Korabecny:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Ondrej Soukup:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Patric Jan Jansson:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Jens Pahnke:** Resources, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Sven Marcel Stefan:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2022.07.062>.

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